

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
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EBT Acceptance Note for

TEBT-2025-0001

Submission Title	Identification of concepts of importance for the assessment of internal validity of in vitro toxicology studies using a modified Delphi technique
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0001
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin ORCID: 0000-0003-2724-7882
Number of Reviewers	1 editor, 2 reviewers
Submission Type	Registered Report (Stage 2)
Preprint DOI	10.5281/zenodo.14656764
Evaluation Stage	Peer-Review
Evaluation Round	Round 3
Evaluation Date	08 August 2025
Recommendation	Revise

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

This manuscript describes the results of the second stage or study of the development of INVITES-IN, a tool for the assessment of the internal validity of in vitro toxicological study. The protocol for the development of the tool including this stage was previously published. In brief, after developing an item bank of 405 concepts of potential relevance, the authors conducted two rounds of a Delphi survey to reach consensus on the item that should be included in the tool. Of

the 405 items in the bank, 372 were included for consideration when assessing potential for bias in an *in vitro* study. The retention of many items from risk-of-bias tools for human and animal studies suggests that some items are applicable across study designs.

The study is well-written and well-documented, including deviations from pre-registered methods, and the editorial triage process only detected a few minor omissions that couldn't be addressed after peer-review. The peer-review process uncovered a few issues with the description of methods or analyses that deserve clarification. Checking for the consistency of language throughout would also improve transparency and readability. Authors revised the manuscript in line with these and all issues were addressed.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Olwenn Martin after 1 round of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 1 round of peer-review.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14767954>.